

**FORMATION OF FRIENDLY RELATIONS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION
CLASSES FOR CHILDREN 6-7 YEARS OLD**

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Resume: This article reveals the current search for effective ways and means of forming relationships that affect the formation of socially valuable qualities of the child's personality and determine his behavior in the society of his peers; orientation of behavior.

Key words: relationship, humanism, personality, benevolence, responsiveness, justice, empathy.

The study of human relations, which has become, according to prominent scientists, the "problem of the century", is a key problem for social psychology. The development of social and emotional intelligence, emotional responsiveness, empathy, the formation of readiness for joint activities with peers, the formation of a respectful attitude and a sense of belonging to one's family and to the community of children and adults in preschools is the content of the social and communicative development of children.

Therefore, the study of the child in the system of his relations with peers in the kindergarten group acquires great importance and relevance, since preschool age is a particularly crucial period in education. It is the age of the initial formation of the child's personality. At this time, in the communication of the child with peers, rather complex relationships arise, which significantly affect the development of his personality.

Communication with children is a necessary condition for the mental development of the child. The need for communication early becomes his basic social need. Communication with peers plays an important role in the life of a preschooler. It is a condition for the formation of the social qualities of the child's

personality, the manifestation and development of the beginnings of friendly relations between children.

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So in his works, the American psychologist T. Shibutani, developing this idea, says that children whose parents keep them from playing with their peers often experience difficulties in relationships in life. He wrote that only "a group of equals accustoms the child to mutual actions and severely corrects mistakes." T. Shibutani suggested that the lack of that experience of a child's communication with peers dulls the ability to understand other people.

Pedagogical and psychological studies show what a big role in shaping the relationship of children with each other can play, which for a small child is not only a school of knowledge of the surrounding world of adults, but also a school of human relations. The way of life of children in kindergarten and the peculiarities of their activities also leave a certain imprint on the relationship of children.

At present, in the theory and practice of preschool pedagogy, more and more importance is attached to children's joint activities as a means of moral education. Joint activities unite children with a common goal, task, joys, sorrows, feelings for a common cause.

Of particular importance in shaping the personality of older preschoolers are relationships that are built on the basis of goodwill. As noted by P.F. Lesgaft, the physical education of children should not be limited only to the improvement and formation of motor skills, it must also be associated with the tasks of moral education. However, to date, these opportunities have not been practically taken into

account and, therefore, they are not sufficiently realized in the motor activity of preschoolers.

The joint motor activity of children, a variety of physical exercises, ways of organizing preschoolers, emotional richness, rhythm, musicality and aesthetics of movements create ample opportunities for accumulating positive experience of interaction between older preschoolers and peers. The social orientation of the individual is manifested and formed in relationships, it is extremely important that humane relations be dominant, one of the important components of which is benevolence.

Benevolent relations are a product of the socially conditioned content of communication. Communication, being the most important social need of a developing personality, is inseparable from relationships. Their bilateral meaningful relationship is emphasized in philosophical, psychological, and pedagogical works. Communication and attitude are two interrelated and interdependent aspects of the phenomenon

“Goodwill is an attitude towards a person, focused on promoting his good, on doing good. Subjectively, benevolence is manifested in goodwill, sympathy, sympathy, beneficence. From a moral point of view, benevolence is a duty of man. Goodwill emphasizes not only the unconditional recognition in another person of his moral dignity, but peacefulness, friendliness, and readiness for fruitful cooperation are expressed.

The benevolent relations of preschoolers in the process of physical education are a general emotional-positive orientation of the child's behavior in his relationships with peers, manifested in the ability to sympathize, understand the state of peers, in readiness to provide assistance and cooperate in joint motor activity.

In modern studies, motor activity is considered as an activity aimed at physical development and motor activity, as a means of versatile influence on the child. In older preschool age, the physical abilities of children increase. Preschoolers already have a good command of most of the main types of motor actions. This makes it

possible to use physical exercises more widely for the purposeful development and education of the child's personality, enriching the culture of communication with peers.

General developmental exercises are performed by children mainly in the frontal way and in all directions. Practically no exercises are carried out in pairs, triples, subgroups without an object, with objects, with one common object (exercises with a long rope, etc.), which prevents the accumulation of valuable experience in a friendly attitude of preschoolers.

The widespread use of joint exercises will contribute to the development of cooperation, which requires the ability to agree, coordinate one's actions with children, respond positively to a mismatch in movements, etc. In the course of the main movements, situations arise that put children in front of the need to help their peers. Preschoolers can be involved in helping each other, which contributes to the development of a caring attitude towards those who need it.

It should be noted that one of the productive forms of the educational process in the system of preschool education, outdoor games and physical exercises, not only improve the health and develop the child's body, but also is a means of educating character, affect the behavior of children.

Outdoor games can be practiced at any time of the year. From one child to the whole group can take part in games, you can play with adults and without their participation

Classes with outdoor games contribute to the education in children of discipline, collectivism, determination, courage and other qualities necessary for every person.

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